

Reconsolidation of CF/PEKK Composites: Repair of Drilling-induced Damage and Hydrothermal-Aging Effects

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Abstract

- Can thermal reconsolidation be used as a viable method to repair drilling-induced damage and mitigate the effects of environmental aging in CF/PEKK composites, thereby restoring their mechanical performance?

- ✓ Thermal reconsolidation repairs drilling-induced damage and mitigates environmental aging
- ✓ Hot-pressing increased compressive strength by up to 37.6%.
- ✓ Enhanced glass transition temperature (T_g) and crystallinity were observed.
- ✓ Reconsolidated samples retained superior performance post-aging.
- ✓ DIC analysis confirmed reduced delamination and restored mechanical integrity.

Methodology

Vacuum Bag Only (VBO) process

- Layup configuration of $[0/45/90/-45]_{3s}$

Hole drilling and hot-wet aging

Reconsolidation

Characterizations

- Thermal characterization
- Thermo-mechanical analyses
- Mechanical tests
- Digital Image Correlation (DIC)

Results and Discussion

Compression and Open-Hole Compression Strengths

Compression test

a. Reference_BA
b. Reconsolidate_BA
c. Reference_AA
d. Reconsolidate_AA

Thermal and Thermo-mechanical Results

Sample	DSC		TGA		DMA	
	T_g (°C)	X_c (%)	T_d (°C)	Mass Loss (%)	E' (GPa)	E'' (MPa)
Reference_BA	146.85±1.30	15.65±0.26	580.90±2.90	12.40±0.17	12.65±1.55	632.97±2.45
Reconsolidate_BA	155.84±1.17	19.26±0.87	582.50±2.38	12.44±0.11	11.39±1.16	531.18±2.75
Reference_AA	155.05±1.92	25.82±1.24	575.54±2.87	13.79±0.23	11.77±1.78	519.82±2.11
Reconsolidate_AA	157.15±1.15	24.88±0.93	580.09±2.88	12.67±0.13	13.69±1.27	560.17±2.26

OHC test

Digital Image Correlation (DIC)

- Full field strain distribution of compression samples at maximum load before and after reconsolidation

- Full field strain distribution of OHC samples at maximum load before and after reconsolidation

Key findings

- Glass transition temperature (T_g) increased by 5.97%.
- Degree of crystallinity (X_c) increased by 20.94%.
- Compressive strength improved by 15.61% in compression samples and 37.61% in Open Hole Compression (OHC) samples before aging.
- Catastrophic aging effects were effectively reversed through reconsolidation.
- DIC analysis showed more uniform strain distribution, restoration of original deformation characteristics, and reduced stress concentrations, lowering the risk of premature failure

Conclusion and Outlook

- ✓ Reconsolidation significantly enhances mechanical properties and structural integrity of CF/PEKK composites after drilling and hot-wet (hydrothermal) aging.
- ✓ Reconsolidation is a promising repair and performance recovery strategy for aerospace-grade thermoplastic composites.
- ✓ Next study: the role of thermal reconsolidation in recovering CF/PEKK composites from single and multiple low-velocity impacts

